

Synthesis of 7-Methyl-4-substituted-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines as Antimicrobial Agents

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THIENOPYRIMIDINES are reported to possess various biological activities¹. Substituted pyrazoles² and aminoguanidines³ also possess biological activities. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to introduce pyrazolyl, amino guanidyl and hydrazinyl groups in tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines and evaluate their antimicrobial activity.

The key intermediate 2-amino-6-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene-3-carboxamide (1) was prepared (Scheme 1) by the reported⁴ method. Cyclisation of 1 with triethyl orthoformate afforded 7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-4-one (2). Reaction of 2 with phosphorus oxychloride gave 4-chloro-7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (3). The chloro compound underwent facile nucleophilic substitution with hydrazine to yield 4-hydrazino-7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (4).

- 6a : R=3,4,5-(OCH₃)₃C₆H₃, R¹=H
 6b : R=4-ClC₆H₄, R¹=H
 6c : R=4-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, R¹=H
 6d : R=3,4-(Cl)₂C₆H₃, R¹=H
 6e : R=2-NO₂C₆H₄, R¹=H
 6f : R=2,4-(OH)₂C₆H₃, R¹=H
 6g : R=4-CN, C₆H₄, R¹=H
 6h : R=3-OCH₃, 4-OH-C₆H₃, R¹=H
 6i : R=CH₃, R¹=4-(CH₃)₂OHCH₂C₆H₄
 6j : R=CH₃, R¹=CH=CH
 6k : R=CH₃, R¹=C₂H₅
 6l : R=CH₃, R¹=CH₂CH(CH₃)₂
 7a : R=4-ClC₆H₄
 7b : R=4-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄
 7c : R=3,4-(Cl)₂C₆H₃
 7d : R=2-NO₂C₆H₄

The 4-hydrazino moiety in turn served as a versatile building block for the preparation of various derivatives.

- a ; R=C≡N, R¹=SCH₃, R²=SCH₃
 b ; R=C≡N, R¹=H, R²=OC₂H₅
 c ; R=COOC₂H₅, R¹=SCH₃, R²=SCH₃
 d ; R=CONH₂, R¹=SCH₃, R²=SCH₃

- a ; R=CH₃, R¹=COOCH₃
 b ; R=C₂H₅, R¹=COOC₂H₅

Scheme 1

The hydrazones (6) were synthesised by condensation of 4 and the appropriate aldehyde or ketone. The hydrazones (6b, c, d, e) were subsequently cyclised to 3-substituted-9-methyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]pyrimido[4,5-*b*]tetrahydrobenzothiofenes (7). The pyrazole group was introduced by the reaction of 4 with 2-substituted-3,3-bismethylmercaptoacrylonitrile/ethoxymethylenemalononitrile (8). The hydrazino derivative 4 on treatment with methyl-*N,N'*-dicarbomethoxy/ethoxycarbamidothioate gave the aminoguanidinyl derivative (11a, b).

Biological activity

Compounds 6a-1, 7a-d, 9a-d and 11a,b were screened against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and various gram-negative bacteria like *Salmonella typhosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Pseudomonas pyocyanase* and *Proteus vulgaris* using ditch plate technique⁵ at concentrations 10 and 20 mg ml⁻¹. Compounds 6a-1 and 9b did not show activity at 10 mg ml⁻¹, but showed varied activity higher concentration. Compounds 7a-d showed activity against all the bacteria at 20 mg ml⁻¹ level. Compounds 9a, c, d, 11a, b also showed activity against all the bacteria at 20 mg ml⁻¹ level.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 681 spectrometer, pmr spectra on Hitachi R-600 and JEOL FX-90 Q spectrometers and mass spectra on a Shimadzu QP-1000 spectrometer.

2-Amino-6-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene-3-carboxamide (1): It was prepared⁴ using 4-methylcyclohexanone, sulphur and cyano acetamide, (60%), m.p. 185° (lit.⁶) (Found : C, 57.10 ; H, 6.61 ; N, 13.29. C₁₀H₁₄N₂OS : calcd. for : C, 57.14 ; H, 6.67 ; N, 13.33%) ; M⁺ m/z 210.

7-Methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-4-one (2): It was synthesised by the reaction of **1** and triethyl orthoformate in toluene, (80%), m.p. 245° (lit.⁶) (Found : C, 60.03 ; H, 5.48 ; N, 12.78. C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₂S calcd. for : C, 60.0 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 12.73%) ; M⁺ m/z 220.

4-Chloro-7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (3): A mixture of **2** (0.1 mol), phosphorus oxychloride (0.15 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. The excess phosphorus oxychloride was then distilled off and the mixture was poured in ice-cold water with stirring. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from methanol, (75%), m.p. 110° (Found C, 55.31 ; H, 4.68 ; N, 11.71. C₁₁H₁₁ClN₂S calcd. for : C, 55.34 ; H, 4.61 ; N, 11.74%) ; M⁺ m/z 238 (Cl=35), 240 (Cl=37).

4-Hydrazino-7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (4): A mixture of **3** (0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.15 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The mixture was then cooled and poured in cold water, and the separated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from methanol, (80%), m.p. 194–195° (Found : C, 56.45 ; H, 5.92 ; N, 23.91. C₁₁H₁₄N₄S calcd. for : C, 56.41 ; H, 5.98 ; N, 23.93%) ; M⁺ m/z 234.

4-Substituted-hydrazono-7-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (6a–l). *General procedure:* A mixture of **4** (10 mmol), an appropriate aldehyde or ketone (**5** ; 12 mmol) and catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (50 mg) in toluene (25 ml) was refluxed for 7 h. The reaction mixture on standing yielded a crystalline solid, which was filtered and washed with hexane. The compound was found to be homogeneous (tlc).

The ir spectrum of **6a** showed absorption band ; ν_{max} 3310 (NH) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N) ; δ (DMSO-d₆+TFA) 1.2 (3H, d, CH₃-CH), 2–3.1 (7H, m, CH₂CH₂CHCH₂), 3.8 (9H, s, (OCH₃)₃), 6.9 (2H, s, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, N=CH-N) and 8.6 (1H, s, N=CH) ; m/z 412 (M⁺) (Table 1).

3-Substituted-9-methyl-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-c]pyrimido[4,5-b]tetrahydrobenzothiophenes (7a–d). *General procedure:* To a solution of (**6b**, **c**, **d**, **e**) (0.90 mmol) and sodium acetate in acetic acid (2 ml) was added bromine (0.1 ml) dissolved in acetic acid (1 ml) dropwise till a clear solution was obtained. It was then left at room temperature for 0.5 h and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised with aqueous sodium carbonate and the solid thus obtained was washed with water and crystallised from water-acetic acid mixture : **7a** M⁺ m/z 354 (Cl=35), 356 (Cl=37) (Table 1).

7-Methyl-4-[3-substituted-5-amino-4-substituted-1H-pyrazole-1-yl]-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (9a–d). *General procedure:* A mixture of **4** (10 mmol), 2-substituted-3,3-bismethylmercaptoacrylonitrile/ethoxymethylenemalononitrile (**8** ; 10 mmol) and catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (50 mg) in toluene (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture on standing yielded a solid, which was crystallised from ethanol :

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd no.	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula/ (mol weight)
6a	223	81	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (412)
6b	204	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ S (356.5)
6c	231	91	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₅ S (365)
6d	198	82	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ S (391)
6e	150	81	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S (367)
6f	240	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S (354)
6g	228	81	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ S (347)
6h	203	83	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S (368)
6i	175	81	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₄ S (392)
6j	230	82	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ S (286)
6k	175	81	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ S (288)
6l	125	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S (316)
7a	291	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₄ S (354.5)
7b	195d	61	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₅ S (363)
7c	201	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ S (389)
7d	220	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₂ S (365)
9a	176	91	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ S ₂ (356)
9b	198	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₆ S (310)
9c	170	91	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ (391)
9d	206	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S (374)
11a	151	77	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S (392)
11b	162	81	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S (420)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

9a ν_{max} (nujol) 2 250 (C≡N) and 3 450 cm⁻¹ (NH₂) ; δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (3H, d, CH-CH₃), 1.8–3.1 (7H, m, CH₂CHCH₂CH₂), 2.6 (3H, s, SCH₃), 5.8 (2H, bs, NH₂ D₂O exchangeable), 8.8 (1H, s, N=CH-N) ; M⁺ m/z 356.

7-Methyl-4-[3,4-dicarbomethoxy/ethoxyaminoguanidin-1-yl]-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (11a, b): A mixture of **4** (10 mmol), methyl-*N, N'*-dicarbomethoxy/ethoxycarbamidothioate (10 mmol) and catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (50 mg) in methanol (40 ml) was stirred for 5 h. The separated solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol : ν_{max} (nujol) 1 730 (COOC₂H₅) and 3 320 cm⁻¹ (NH) ; δ (DMSO-d₆+TFA) 1.2–1.5 (9H, m, CH-CH₃) and (-OCH₂CH₃)₂, 2.0–3.1 (7H, m, CH₂CH-CH₂-CH₂), 4.0–4.4 (4H, m, (-OCH₂CH₃)₂), 8.2 (N=CH-N). The nmr spectrum was recorded in DMSO-d₆+TFA, because of the rapid exchange the NH protons were not observed.

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